

Fungal Pathogens Responsible for Diseases in Carrot (*Daucus Carota* L.) Production in Ondo State Nigeria

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Abstract

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) is a vegetable that is mostly eaten raw without cooking. It therefore serves as a vehicle for fungi to move from farm to stomach, these microflora are also responsible for carrot spoilage leading to losses. In this study, fungi the causing diseases in carrot production were investigated. Carrots were purchased from local farmers in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, labeled appropriately and taken to the laboratory for analyses. The carrots were divided into 2 groups (A and B). Group A was further divided into subgroups and kept in refrigerator (4 ± 2 °C) and colanders (30 ± 2 °C) to study the fungi responsible for its spoilage, group B was used to determine the fungi present on carrot. The fungi present on the surface of spoilt carrots and fresh carrots were isolated by scraping the surface of the carrot with sterile knife on sterile aluminium foil. One gram of the scrapped carrot surface was weighed aseptically and diluted serially to dilution 10^{-3} . Saboraud agar (SA) and potato dextrose agar (PDA) were used for the culturing, and incubated at 28 °C for 72 hours. The morphology of the pure fungus on plate was observed for its shape, colour (front and reverse) under the microscope using x10 and x40 objectives. *Sacharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Pleurothecium recurvatum* and *Rhizopus nigricans* were the fungi isolated from the surface of fresh carrots while (*Sclerotini sclerotiorum*, *Penicillium natatum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizopus nigricans*) were isolated from spoilt carrot. Some of the fungi found on the fresh carrots are pathogenic, fungal species like *A. niger* could produce toxic metabolites in the affected sites, constituting a potential health hazard for humans, *Sclerotini sclerotiorum* causes devastating losses to farmers. It is therefore important to look for means of inhibiting the growth of these fungi on carrots to prevent food borne diseases and loss of farm produce.

Keywords: Food-borne diseases, food spoilage, microflora, carrots, fungi

INTRODUCTION

Carrot (*Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus*) is a root vegetable, typically orange in colour, though varies including purple, black, red, white, and yellow cultivars exist, all of which are domesticated forms of the wild carrot, *Daucus carota*, native to Europe and Southwestern Asia (Singn *et al.*, 2021).

The plant probably originated in Iran and was originally cultivated for its leaves and seeds. The characteristic orange colour is from beta-carotene, making carrots a rich source of vitamin A. It is associated with heart and eye health, improved digestion, and even weight loss (Singn *et al.*, 2021). Carrots are a nutrient-dense root vegetable with a variety of health benefits. Besides beta-carotene, carrots contain lutein, zeaxanthin, and other phytonutrients that protect cells from oxidative stress. Despite their sweet taste, carrots have a low glycemic index, so they do not spike blood sugar significantly (Silva-Dias, 2014). All these qualities make carrot an important vegetable. Unfortunately, carrots are highly perishable because of its high moisture content and loads of microorganisms on its surface being a root vegetable (Motegoonkar *et al.* (2024)), making it difficult to keep for a longer period.

Fungi are eukaryotic, non-vascular, non-motile and heterotrophic organisms, it may be unicellular or filamentous that includes microorganisms such as yeasts, molds and mushrooms. Most fungi are decomposers; they feed on organic matter and cause various degree of spoilage of farm produce. Some of these fungi are also pathogenic attacking both animal and plant. In plants, fungi can destroy plant tissue directly or through the production of potent toxins, which usually ends in host death (Samanta, 2015). Fungi are significant pathogens of carrots, causing a variety of diseases that can lead to severe pre- and post-harvest losses. The major fungi diseases affecting carrots are *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* causing watery soft rot, *Rhizopus stolonifer* responsible for soft rot, *Fusarium spp.* cause dry rot, *Penicillium spp.* causes blue or green mold, *Alternaria spp.* causes black rot or black spot on carrots.

Due to high load of fungi on carrot surface being a root vegetable coupled with high moisture content, farmers face a lot of problem in storing carrot. Carrot farmers, especially in developing regions, often face several storage-related problems that affect both quality and profitability. Carrots require cool (0 – 4°C) and humid (90 – 95%) conditions (Motegoonkar *et al.*, 2024), which are difficult to maintain without infrastructure and many smallholder farmers lack access to refrigerated storage, leading to rapid spoilage due to inadequate storage, carrots often rot or shrink within days, resulting in significant losses. It becomes worthwhile to investigate the pathogenic fungi associated with carrots in order to prevent spoilage and provide a basis for future control measures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Carrots

Fresh carrots were purchased from various markets located at different areas of Akure (Oja-Oba, Isinkan, FUTA gate and Shasha), Ondo State, Nigeria. Each sample was kept in different clean polythene bags and labeled appropriately. From each bag carrots were taken for further experiments.

Isolation and Identification of fungi present on fresh carrots bought from different markets

The microorganisms present on the surface of carrots bought from the various markets were isolated by scraping the surface of the carrot with sterile knife on sterile aluminium foil. One gram of the scrapped carrot surface was weighed aseptically into universal bottle, separate bottle for different sample and diluted serially to dilution 10^{-3} . From the 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} dilution tubes, 1ml was taken and pipetted into sterile petri dishes respectively in triplicates to culture fungi. Sterile

molten agars at 45°C (saboraud agar (SA) and potato dextrose agar (PDA)) were used and were incubated at 28°C for 72 hours. After incubation, the colonies were counted and isolated colonies were streaked onto a new plate SA and PDA and incubated at appropriate temperatures to obtain a pure culture. The isolates were identified according to Samson *et al.* (2010). This was done for all the carrots bought at different markets respectively.

The morphology of the pure fungus on plate was observed for its shape, colour (front and reverse). The microscope studies of the pure fungi isolated were done by mounting a bit of each colony into a drop of distilled water on a glass slide. It was then thinned out with a pin, stained with methylene blue to view the hyphal structures and lactophenol cotton blue was used for the observation of septate or non-septate hypha under the microscope using x10 and x40 objectives.

Isolation and Identification of Microorganisms on Spoilt Carrot during Storage at 4 ± 2°C

Carrots bought from different markets in Ondo State were stored at 4 ± 2°C and 27 ± 2°C respectively and were monitored for signs of spoilage. The fungi isolated were identified according to Samson *et al.* (2010).

Pathogenicity Test on Fungi Isolated from Spoilt Carrots during Storage

Microorganisms isolated from spoilt carrot were further subjected to test to determine the actual microorganisms responsible for the spoilage using a modified method of Kahala *et al.* (2012). Fresh wholesome carrots were washed with potable water, sterilized with vinegar (60% concentration) for 30 minutes then rinsed with sterile distilled water and allowed to dry. These were grouped into eight (2 carrots per group). Each group was inoculated with different microorganisms isolated from spoilt carrot and packed in sterile aluminum foil and sterile food bags respectively and stored at 30 ± 2°C. The infected carrots were observed daily for signs of spoilage.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Fungi Present on the Surface of Fresh Carrots

Eight fungi *Mucor mucedo*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Sacharomyces cerevisiae*, *Penicillium italicum*, *Peacilomyces viriotii*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Pleurothecium recurvatum* were isolated (Table 1). The most frequently encountered microorganisms was *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (100%), it was isolated from all the carrots bought at different markets.

Table 1: Frequency of occurrence of types of fungi on the surface of carrots bought from different markets in Akure.

Types of microorganisms	Frequency of occurrence (%)					
	A	B	C	D	Total	Percentage
<i>Mucor mucedo</i>	+	+	-	-	2	50
<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	-	-	-	+	1	25

<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	+	+	+	+	4	100
<i>Penicillium italicum</i>	-	-	+	-	1	25
<i>Peacilomyces viriotii</i>	+	-	+	-	2	50
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	+	-	-	-	1	25
<i>Rhizopus nigrican</i>	-	+	-	-	1	25
<i>Pleurothecium recurvatum</i>	-	-	-	+	1	25

Key:

A- Oja- Oba market
B- FUTA area

C- Shasha market
D- Isinkan market

Fungi Isolated from Spoilt Carrots during Storage at 4 ± 2 °C and 30 ± 2 °C

Fungi isolated from spoilt carrots stored at 30 ± 2 °C are *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Mucur Mucedo* and only four fungi were isolate from carrots kept at 4 ± 2 °C as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Fungi Isolated from Spoilt Carrots during Storage at 4 ± 2 °C and 30 ± 2 °C

Isolates	Storage Temperature	
	4 ± 2 °C	30 ± 2 °C
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	-	+
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	-	+
<i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i>	-	+
<i>Penicillium notatum</i>	+	+
<i>Rhizopus nigricans</i>	+	+
<i>Mucur Mucedo</i>	+	+

Pathogenicity of Fungi Isolated from Spoilt Carrots during Storage

Five out of the six fungi isolated from spoilt carrots; *S. sclerotiorum*, *P. notatum*, *R. nigricans* and *Mucur Mucedo*, *A. niger* were responsible for spoilage of carrots in the spoilage test.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the impact of fungi isolated from carrots on carrot spoilage and associated health risks. Some of fungi isolated from carrots are known to contribute to post-harvest spoilage and may pose health risks due to the production of mycotoxins or other harmful metabolites. Out of the eight fungi isolated from carrots bought from different markets in Ondo State, Nigeria, one was found to be pathogenic (*A. flavus*). *Aspergillus flavus* is known to produce aflatoxin (Fakruddin *et al.*, 2015) which can cause food intoxication. Some other organisms isolated; *S. sclerotiorum*, *P. notatum*, *R. nigricans*, *Mucur Mucedo*, and *A. niger* were responsible for spoilage of carrots. Farmers experience great losses after harvest as a result of these fungi found on carrots. Some of these fungi contaminate carrots right from field and during transportation (Alegbeleye *et al.*, 2018). Carrots stored at low temperature were spoilt by fewer fungi (Table 2) and no pathogenic fungus was isolated, this explained why low storage temperatures help in food

preservation and reduced cases of foodborne illnesses caused by pathogenic fungi, although some of these fungi were still able to grow at 4°C (Goswami *et al.*, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Five out of eight fungi isolated from carrots surface were found to be spoilage organisms, and one is pathogenic to man. Farmers are advised to prevent or control fungi contamination right from the field. As carrots are root vegetables, they are particularly susceptible to contamination by spoilage organisms present in soil. Therefore, farmers are encouraged to implement crop rotation to reduce soil-borne fungal pathogen, use seeds that are resistant to diseases and irrigate their farms using clean water.

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